

Short communication

**New synonymies in the genera *Cymindis* and *Brachinus*
(Coleoptera: Carabidae) in Iran**

Jan Muilwijk^{1&*} & Marjan Seedy²

1- Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, The Netherlands & 2- School of Biology and Center of Excellence in Phylogeny of Living Organism, College of Science, University of Tehran, Tehran, Iran.

* Corresponding author, E-mail: Jan.Muilwijk@gmail.com

مترادف‌های جدید جنس‌های *Brachinus* و *Cymindis* (Coleoptera: Carabidae) در ایران

یان مویلویک^{۱*} و مرجان سیدی^۲

۱- مرکز مطالعات تنوع زیستی طبیعی، لایدن، هلند و ۲- دانشکده زیست‌شناسی و مرکز قطب تبارزایی موجودات زنده، پردیس علوم، دانشگاه تهران، تهران، ایران.

* مسئول مکاتبات، پست الکترونیکی: Jan.Muilwijk@gmail.com

چکیده

Lebia zabolii Jedlička 1968 و *Cymindis (Cymindis) petrovitzi* Mandl 1973 در اینجا به ترتیب به عنوان مترادف‌های جدید *Brachinus (Cnecostolus) bagdatensis* Pic 1902 و *Cymindis (Petrovitzella) persica* و *Brachinus (INCERTAE)* و *Cymindis (Cymindis) transversa* Morvan 1972 تلقی می‌شوند. *Jedlička* 1968 نیز به ترتیب مترادف‌های جدید *strictus* Morvan 1971 و *Cymindis (Cymindis) picta* (Pallas, 1771) در نظر گرفته می‌شوند. واژگان کلیدی: *Cymindis*, *Brachinus*, Carabidae، ایران و مترادف.

دریافت: ۱۳۹۶/۱/۲۶، پذیرش: ۱۳۹۶/۲/۲۵.

During our research on the Iranian Carabidae, we studied the type material of several species of which we found four new synonymies in the genera *Cymindis* and *Brachinus*.

Acronyms of the collections:

MNHN: Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris

NMB: Naturhistorisches Museum, Basel

***Lebia zabolii* Jedlička 1968**

The description of *Lebia zabolii* was based on a female which is housed in MNHN and labelled as: Iran, Zabol/ 20.IV.1965// Museum Paris// Mission Franco-Iranienne, 1965// Paratypus, *Lebia zabolii* sp.n. /det. Ing. Jedlička/Nat. Prague// inv. 23576.

We compared the types of *Lebia zabolii* and *Brachinus bagdatensis* Pic, 1902 and realized that *Lebia zabolii* (Figure 1) is a synonymy of *B. bagdatensis* (Figure 2). In the collection of Morvan (Carentoir, France), a specimen of *B. bagdatensis* was identified by Jedlička as *Brachinus zabolii* (sic). Jedlička (1961) described the same species as *Cymindis richteri*.

Fig. 1. *Lebia zaboli*, holotype, scale bar = 2mm.

Fig. 2. *Brachinus bagdatensis*, holotype, scale bar = 2mm.

***Cymindis (Cymindis) petrovitzi* Mandl 1973**

The description of *Cymindis petrovitzi* was based on a female which is housed in NMB and labelled as: Dasht-arjan/ W. Shiraz, Iran/ leg. Petroviz// Holotypus *Petrovitzia petrovitzi* /Mandl (red label) // *Petroviziella persica* Jedl./ det. Morvan 1975 (handwritten).

Mandl (1973) erected the new genus *Petroviziella* and described two species *Petroviziella petrovitzi* and *P. vartianorum*. Löbl & Smetana (2003) considered the genus *Petroviziella* as the subgenus *Cymindis*. The species *Cymindis petrovitzi* was included in *Cymindis* s.str. and *C. vartianorum* which was placed in the subgenus *Petroviziella*. The genus name had been written as *Petrovitzia* on the label of the holotype. The genus name *Petrovitzia* had been occupied by Mikšić (1965). Mandl (1973) had used *Petrovitzia* and apparently forgot to correct it. Since the other data of the examined specimen match with the data of the publication, we conclude that this specimen is the holotype and the genus name of the type label was intact.

Mandl (1973) failed to cite Jedlička (1968) containing the description of *Cymindis persica*, probably because he was not aware of this species. We compared the types of the both species and found that *C. petrovitzi* (Figure 3) is a synonymy of *C. persica*.

According to the labels of *C. petrovitzi*, Morvan had concluded that this species was a synonymy of *C. persica* but he left it unpublished. Here we follow Morvan's conclusion about this synonymy.

***Cymindis (Cymindis) transversa* Morvan 1972**

The description of *Cymindis transversa* was based on a female which is housed in Morvan's personal collection (Carentoir, France) and labelled as: Iran, Fars/ Khankhoreh/ VI-1970/ P. Morvan// *Cymindis transversum* Morvan// Holotype (red label).

Fig. 3. *Cymindis petrovitzi*, holotype, scale bar = 2mm.

Morvan (1972) stated the resemblance between this species and *Cymindis* (*Cymindis*) *picta* (Pallas, 1771) in the description. We noticed distinct contrast between the dark spot and yellowish colour of elytra and darker antennomeres IV–IX. Other characters of *C. transversa* agrees with *C. picta*. *Cymindis* species can vary in the colour pattern of the elytra. In the studied material we saw the following variations of the colour of the antennae: in some specimens all antennomeres were light-coloured; in other specimens antennomeres IV–IX were darker than the first three. Therefore, we consider *C. transversa* (Figure 4) as a junior synonymy of *C. picta*.

Fig. 4. *Cymindis transversa*, holotype, scale bar = 2mm.

***Brachinus* (INCERTAE) *strictus* Morvan 1971**

The holotype of *Brachinus strictus* is preserved in MNHN (according to the description), and a female allotype is kept in Morvan collection (Carentoir, France). We failed to access the holotype. The allotype is labelled as: Iran, VII de Chalus/ 2700 m VII.1968/ nord ouest, P. Morvan (handwritten)// *Brachinus strictus*/ Morvan// Allotype (red label).

The presence of hairs on the light coloured membrane at the apex of the elytra, that was not mentioned by Morvan (1971), led to its treatment as Incertae sedis subgenus (Löbl & Smetana, 2003). In fact the species belongs to the subgenus *Brachinus* s.str. because of the presence of scattered long hairs on apical membrane. The original description and the characteristics fit exactly with the features of *Brachinus (Brachinus) crepitans* (L., 1758). *B. crepitans* is commonly found in Iran. Therefore, we consider *B. strictus* (Figure 5) as a junior synonymy of *B. (Brachinus) crepitans*.

Fig. 5. *Brachinus strictus*, holotype, scale bar = 2mm

Acknowledgements

The authors express their sincere thanks to Matthias Borer (Naturhistorisches Museum, Basel), Azadeh Taviglian (Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris) and Pierre Morvan (Carentoir, France) for providing the material. Oscar Vorst gave us valuable advice to solve the confusion surrounding *C. petrovitzia* for which we are grateful.

References

- Jedlička A.** (1968) Contribution à la faune de l'Iran. II. Nouveaux Coléoptères Carabidae. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France (N.S.)* 4, 989–996.
- Löbl, I. & Smetana, A.** (Eds.) (2003) *Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Volume 1. Archostemata - Myxophaga - Adephaga*. 819 pp. Stenstrup: Apollo Books.
- Mandl, K.** (1973) Bausteine zur Kenntnis der Familie Carabidae (Col.). *Entomologische Arbeiten aus dem Museum G. Frey* (24), 88–100.
- Mikšić, R.** (1965) Achter Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Protaetia arten neue Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Protaetien der Republik Indonesien und der benachbarten Gebiete. *Entomologische Abhandlungen und Berichte aus dem Staatlichen Museum für Tierkunde in Dresden* (31), 265–306.

Morvan P. (1971) Nouveaux coléoptères carabiques d'Iran. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France (N.S.)* 7, 231–239.

Morvan P. (1972) Description de nouveaux coléoptères carabiques d'Iran. *Bulletin de la Société Entomologique de France* 77, 26–28.
